

ISic3686

Theodoros offers a dedication to Serapis

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

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Autopsy

2017-07-17

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Found in the section of the trench on the west side of the so-called 'muro a bugnato', which borders the main street and the area of the so-called 'lower agora', to the north-east of the main agora

Coordinates

37.998330, 14.263051

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 30589

Physical Description

Part of a fine white limestone block, forming the base of a statue (two circular holes, 5.5cm in diameter, are visible in the front part of the upper surface, the left c.5 cm from the front, the right c.7.5 cm from the front; the right hole is incomplete). The block is intact on top, as well as on the front and left; it is broken at the rear and on the right; c.14 cm high. Perhaps half the block is lost on the right. The face is damaged on the left, and below, as well as on the right, with minor damage along the top edge.

Dimensions

Height 14 cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Greek text is visible on three lines, as much as half the text lost on the right side.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are deeply and broadly cut with plain strokes lacking serifs. Omega is closed and slightly ovoid; omicron is full size.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 18-20 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. (vac.undefined)Σεράπ[ιδικαι "Ισιδι]
2. Θεόδωρο[ς][---]

3. (vac.undefined)M[---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

To Serapis (?and Isis?). Theodoros [(dedicated this)----]

Commentary

The first line appears to contain a dedication to the god Serapis. Dedications to Serapis are commonly twinned with Isis, and this would fit with the likely extent of the original stone. The second line would then contain the name of the man (Theodoros) making the dedication, together with the name of his father. The third line might then contain a reference to his current position, or his reason for the dedication, but whatever it was, there is little space since the word/ words are clearly centered and there is blank space before hand. This is the only evidence from Halaesa for a cult of Serapis, but Hellenistic dedications to Serapis and Isis are known from both Siracusa (IG XIV.14a = ISic3002 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3002>] – Serapis is a very plausible restoration) and Taormina (IG 14.433 = ISic1258 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1258>]).

The form of the letters suggests a date in the second or first century BC.

Digital identifiers:

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3686>

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.4021607](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021607)

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.4

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Photo J. Prag courtesy Soprintendenza BBCCAA di Messina